

The Perception Of Students Towards Online Teaching-Learning During Covid 19

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Abstract

This study attempts to find out the perception of the students towards online teaching-learning during second wave of COVID 19 in India. Purposive sampling has been done. The sample consists of 214 school and college going students of Bijnor (U P). The survey has been done online through Google form consisting of 10 closed ended items. Findings revealed that 47% of sample preferred offline/physical classroom teaching as most effective mode of Teaching-learning followed by blended mode (33%) and online mode (20%). For synchronous mode Google meet and for asynchronous mode YouTube are the most preferred platform for online teaching-learning. Internet availability and connectivity issue has been considered as biggest obstacle for online learning-teaching by the sample students.

Key words: Online learning, Online teaching, Perception, Blended learning, Synchronous mode, Asynchronous mode

1.0 Introduction:

The global COVID 19 pandemic has shattered the economic, political, commercial, administrative and educational systems of many countries. In India, Lockdowns were announced in Kerala on 23 March and in the rest of the country on 25 March ("COVID-19 Pandemic in India," 2021). By mid-May 2020, during the first wave of COVID 19, there was a challenge to fight and overcome the new unexpected pandemic situation. Every country fought with the pandemic situation in its own ways. Like every other nation the COVID 19 pandemic situation has posed a lot of challenges in the Indian education system also. As no physical classroom teaching was possible due to strict lockdown and COVID Protocol, digital and online learning emerged as a savior of the education and learning of students. During the first wave of COVID 19, educational administrators, teachers, and students were not well acquainted with and skilled in online teaching, learning and administration. But, slowly and gradually they learnt it as there was no way possible in a pandemic situation. After the first wave, when the education institutions have just started normalizing towards normal practice of real physical teaching and learning, the country witnessed a second wave of COVID 19 attack in the month of April 2021. Another set of lockdowns again posed a serious problem before policy makers to meet the challenge. This time, students, teachers and educational administrators have become more skilled and equipped for digital and online teaching learning. They have become used to and accepted the online and digital format of teaching and learning. Just after the declaration of lockdown, schools and colleges shifted themselves to online classes from

offline/physical classes as per the guidelines released by central and state governments. Students engage themselves in online classes as well as online learning through various E resources.

As per Bentley et al., 2012, Learning systems by integrating internet connections with teaching and learning processes are identified as online learning systems or virtual learning systems. Bower et al., 2015; Hoi et al., 2018; Landrum et al., 2020; and Smith et al., 2019 considered that In an online learning environment, face to face interaction is replaced by virtual interaction which provides convenience and flexibility (Rojabi, 2020). Basically online learning is being carried out by synchronous and asynchronous platforms. Synchronous learning means that the teacher and the students in the course engage with the course content and each other at the same time, but from different locations. Asynchronous learning means that the teacher and the students in the course engage with the course content at different times (and from different locations) (*Synchronous and Asynchronous Online Learning*, 2020). The content may be recorded text, pdf, slides, audio and video.

In India, the synchronous live online classes have never been in regular practice in schools and higher education institutes. But to cope up with the situation of pandemic, schools and colleges have started using Google meet, Zoom, Cisco Webex, etc predominantly for online live teaching. Learning Management systems (LMS) such as Microsoft teams, Google Classroom etc have also been used by some financially and technologically empowered educational institutes. The most dominant problem with the use of synchronous platforms is that some students might not be able to participate at the required time due to technical or scheduling problems. So along with synchronous platforms, students are using asynchronous platforms as well for their learning. Youtube, Google search engines, Open Education Resources, Massive open online courses, Learning Apps, and Government initiatives as online learning platforms such as SWAYAM, DIKSHA, e-Pathshala, etc.

All these online resources have been gaining popularity at this crucial time of the pandemic, as there is no choice for the learning community to cope with the situation. But, there exist some obstacles/challenges with online learning such as financial feasibility of teachers, students and educational institutions, digital divide, internet connectivity in semi urban and rural areas etc.

Perception is the experience of object, event, relationship acquired by resuming information and interpreting message. It gives a meaning towards stimulus-response in resuming information and predicting message which involves attention, hope, motivation and memory (Rakhmat, 2000). Students are the most important unit of teaching learning process and for sustaining the learning and teaching of them this whole digital/online learning drill has been carried out by all the educational institutes. Therefore, the perception of students towards online learning has a great impact upon knowing the effectiveness of online teaching learning process. There is dearth of studies which explore the attitudes and perceptions of students towards online teaching and learning during the second phase of COVID 19. The present study is just to get an idea about that perception of theirs.

2.0 Objective:

- To study the perception of students towards online teaching and learning during the second phase of COVID 19.

3.0 Method:

A questionnaire using Google form was created and used for the online survey. All the students of secondary schools and colleges of Bijnor district in Uttar Pradesh (India) were considered as the population of the study. As it was not possible to reach a substantial number of students as a sample, all those students of secondary schools and colleges who participated in this online survey through Google form were considered as the Sample for the study. The questionnaire consisted of 10 close-ended questions to gain an idea about the students' involvement in online learning and their perception of online learning. The data received through close-ended questions were used to obtain the percentage of the analysed section.

4.0 Results and Discussion:

Before going in detail about the results the characteristics of participants are summarised below in Table 1 and pie chart (Figure 1).

Table: 1

Educational Institutions	Gender		Total
	Male	Female	
School	26	23	49
College	35	130	165
Total	61	153	214

As indicated above in Table:1 and Figure:1, the overall sample consists of 165 college students and 49 school students i.e. about 77% of College students and 23% of secondary school students respectively. The less participation percentage of secondary school students may be due to their restricted approach to the devices (smartphones, laptop etc.) used for responding through Google form. In terms of Gender 71% female and 29% male students have participated in the survey. From Table 1, it can be concluded that female students of colleges participated in a great number i.e. almost 84% of total female student participants. This indicates that female students are inclined more towards online learning and are keen to share their experiences and perception towards online learning.

Figure:1

From the responses about their engagement in online learning, it is concluded that only 187 out of 214 i.e. 87% of students are engaged in online learning (Figure:2). From this, it can also be inferred that 13% of students who have access to the hardware devices have not shown involvement/interest in online learning.

Figure:2

Responses regarding the Hardware device/s students prefer to use for online learning revealed that 86% of students engaged in online learning prefer Smartphone as a device. Only 12 % preferred laptop as a device for online learning. Figure:3 depicts the above statements. Personal Computers and Tablets were preferred by a negligible number of students. The popularity of smart phones among learner may be due to the reason that Smart phones are comparatively cheaper and available in almost every house hence is easily available to students (even from Economically Weaker Sections) for online learning during COVID 19 pandemic.

Figure:3

On the item, whether students have ever attended live online classes, 173 out of 187 students i.e. In this regard, Figure: 4 indicates that 93% of the students who are engaged in online learning responded positively. Whereas, only 7 % of such students accepted that they have never attended live online classes. This clearly indicates that the drive of schools and colleges to conduct live online classes in the time of pandemic has been accepted by the students and they are attending live online classes as an alternative to their physical offline classes.

Figure:4

The use of these platforms varies from institution to institution and teacher to teacher. Some of the institutions are using Learning Management System software such as Microsoft Teams whereas some institutions have left the choice of platform on the teachers for taking live online classes. So, students have to experience various teaching-learning applications for attending live online classes. While getting information about the platform preferred by them for live online classes it has been found that 56% of the students prefer Google Meet followed by Zoom App (37%) and Microsoft Teams (4%) as projected in Figure:5. Whereas, Lakshman Naik et al., 2021 considered Zoom app as the most preferred one followed by Google Meet for online live classes. The reason for the popularity of Google meet might be due to the reason that almost everyone has a Google account and it is part and parcel of that account, so students have no need to download any extra application. Apart from that Google meet is easy to handle live online classes.

Figure:5

Figure:6 informs about the asynchronous online learning mode the students' sample use. The data shows that 40% of students prefer to use you-tube for asynchronous online learning followed by whatsapp (27%) and learning apps (13%). Youtube is a free user friendly application having collections of videos under many sections. Teachers' and learning community prefer to create and upload their educational videos on various topics in this platform. Whatsapp is an equally popular free messaging application but it is just a messaging app through which you can share text, media, links and docs to your whatsapp contact numbers and groups. Learners having smart phones and internet connectivity feel themselves comfortable using the abovementioned applications in

comparison to another asynchronous online learning platform. Learning applications are popular amongst those students who are preparing for any competitive exams.

Figure:6

Figure:7 depicts the data collected for knowing about the learners’ preferred mode for their effective online learning indicates that only 9% of the learner preferred Asynchronous/Recorded online learning as an effective mode of learning. 29% of online learners preferred Live/Synchronous online classes for effective learning, whereas, 62% of online learners of schools and colleges prefer the blend of both Synchronous and Asynchronous mode as an effective online learning mode.

Figure:7

While knowing about the benefits which the sample learners get from online learning, the collected data as depicted in Figure:8 indicates that 44% of students like online learning because it develops self-discipline and time management sense in them. 30% of sample students consider online learning beneficial for its flexibility i.e. students can learn as per their suitable time and place. 10% of the students consider online learning as beneficial for its cost-effectiveness. 8% of students like it as it refined critical thinking skills in them. 6% of students find online learning beneficial because of availability of ample resources.

Figure:8

On the item asking for limitations in online learning, As seen in Figure:9, 63% of students find internet connectivity as the greatest obstacle to engage in online learning. Research conducted by Arasaratnam-Smith & Northcote, 2017; Claywell et al., 2016; and Sun & Chen, 2016 also came to the same conclusion. 13% of the students find distracted concentration as a limitation in online learning. Lack of two-way interaction in online learning has been considered as a limitation by 11% of students. Health hazards are considered as a limitation in online learning by 9% of students.

Figure:9

While asked about the most effective mode of learning from the sample students, 47% of the students find offline physical/real classroom teaching/learning as the most effective mode of learning. According to 33% of students, the Blended learning mode (mixture of both online and offline) is the most effective mode of learning. This is almost in line with the UGC’s public notice of 20th May 2021. Only 20% of students considered the online learning/teaching mode as the most effective mode of learning.

Figure:10

5.0 Conclusion:

As a conclusion, we come to know that the online mode of learning, which is the principal mode of learning during COVID 19, is considered as the least effective mode among the students. It seems that the online learning mode is just a weak measure to compensate for the traditional teaching-learning of school and college-going students. Only 20% of sample students preferred it as an effective mode of learning. 47% of the participating students considered offline physical/real classroom teaching/learning as the most effective mode of learning which is in line with the findings of Lakshman Naik et al., (2021). Whereas, 33% of the participants found Blended mode of learning (mixture of online and offline learning) as the most effective mode of learning. The University Grants Commission (UGC) has also issued a concept note on blended mode of teaching and learning in universities and colleges. According to the draft guidelines, higher education institutions (HEIs) may be allowed to teach up to 40% of the syllabus of each course through online mode and the remaining 60% through offline teaching (<https://www.educationtimes.com> dated May 22, 2021). So, from the perception of students, it is evident that the physical/real/offline learning and teaching cannot replace the online teaching and learning. Rather online teaching and learning can only act as a supportive hand to the traditional offline/real face to face teaching and learning.

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